

128 × 128 Pixel CMOS Event Camera With Multi-Bit Temporal Difference Event Generation

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Abstract—This paper presents 128 × 128 pixel CMOS event camera front-end and its ADC that can produce multi-bit temporal difference events from subsequent pixel intensity values. The implementation was done with 180 nm CMOS technology. The designs of the pixel front-end, column ADC, FPN compensation, as well as their simulation and measurement results, are presented. Our implementation uses temporal events to construct a grayscale frame without the need to a full range ADC. This approach provides a means to have pixel grayscale values that are in sync with temporal difference events, wherein having access to both grayscale information and temporal difference events could be useful in further processing steps that are needed in applications such as moving object detection and classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

CMOS event sensors respond to local changes in pixel intensity and typically use a regulated continuous time (non-integrating) pixel front-end. They offer several advantages over integrating pixel front-ends such as high temporal resolution, high dynamic range, less under/overexposure and motion blur. These properties make them suitable for low-latency object detection and tracking in time-critical applications. However, detection and recognition of moving objects would be more effective if grayscale information is available.

Some event cameras can also capture grayscale data, for example [1], combines regulated and integrating capabilities at pixel level, whereas [2], uses a dual pixel with regulated and time-to-threshold operation. Both of these approaches produce grayscale information that is not in sync with the events. The events react much faster to changes in the visual scene and in fast moving scenes the grayscale information is not up-to-date. In effect, plain positive and negative temporal difference events carry information about visual features such as texture and light intensity. However, that information is not readily available and reconstructing the intensity information from temporal difference events requires intensive compute in spatial and temporal domain [3].

In this paper, our approach is to use a regulating pixel front-end, scan the rows of pixels in regular intervals and use this information to compare the difference of absolute values in subsequent scans of a row, thus providing a means to quickly construct and store grayscale information. We present a temporal difference event camera that contains a multi-bit event analog-to-digital converter (ADC) shared by a

column of pixels in a time-multiplexed manner. The design is implemented with 180 nm CMOS fabrication technology.

In our work, the proposed ADC converts the difference of the latest stored reference signal and instantaneous pixel output. The reference is stored in a digital memory (8-bits) and converted to analog with a resistor array DAC. The stored reference is updated based on the ADC result so that the latest stored reference always approaches the instantaneous sensor output. If the ADC process is carried out frequently as compared to the rate of change of the pixel signal, the latest stored reference and instantaneous sensor output differ from each other by only a small number of comparison levels. In contrast to typical event camera where events are read out asynchronously from the sensor array, the proposed scheme produces the events at synchronous time intervals. Column parallel ADC and event generation simplifies the pixel implementation compared to e.g. [4]. Difference-based ADC circuitry allows for faster comparison compared to carrying out full range ADC operations. As the ADC is performed only at the vicinity — distance in number of comparison levels is configurable — of the stored previous reference value, high speed conversion while maintaining monotonic behaviour and accuracy can be obtained with a compact circuitry.

An example of a guaranteed monotonic ADC is a thermometer ADC, where the signal is successively compared to quantization levels, where each successive level is one LSB apart from the previous comparison. Since the difference between the instantaneous and stored values can be either positive or negative, a signed thermometer ADC is used to first determine the sign of the difference and then perform thermometer type successive comparisons to determine the absolute value of the difference. The ADC itself produces the difference information and there is no need for a separate digital comparator. Furthermore, converted and updated data is readily available for further on-chip processing, e.g. event processing, outside of the sensor array.

II. PIXEL FRONTEND

The pixel front-end shown in Fig. 1, consists of a widely used regulated front-end structure followed by buffer stages in order to isolate the bitline from the photodiode voltage. The readout from the pixel consists of precharging the readline to precharge voltage $VSSRESET$ that is lower than the possible lower end of the pixel dynamic range and then accessing a particular pixel row by a row select switch allowing the final buffer stage to pull up the readline to the desired voltage.

Fig. 1. Pixel frontend schematic.

According to simulations, a decade change in the illumination results in 40–50 mV change of output voltage at the readline. The maximum output swing is approximately 350 mV which corresponds to 140 dB dynamic range. However the mismatches limit the effective dynamic range closer to 100 dB. We acknowledge that the sensor’s dynamic range is limited in dark by noise, which is yet to be measured. However, based on the sensor’s simulation model the dynamic range is mismatch limited. Monte Carlo simulations showed that the standard deviation mismatch between two pixels at column ADC input is 17 mV. The pixel size is $10\mu\text{m} \times 10\mu\text{m}$.

III. COLUMN ADC, MEMORIES AND READOUT

The block level diagram of chip operation is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of a comparator, counters, a resistor array based DAC, a thermocode generator, event detection circuitry, an 8-bit frame memory, a 6-bit compensation memory and a readout circuitry. The ADC sequence starts with uploading the corresponding previous pixel value from the frame memory to an up/down counter. The previous value is also used as an input to the DAC, that provides a reference voltage to the comparator. Once the comparator has its inputs, i.e. the readline voltage to be converted and the DAC output representing the previous pixel ADC result, the comparator checks if the new pixel value has changed from the previous value up or down by a programmable amount. The sign extraction is enabled by setting the LSB of the thermometer counter $T<0>$ to HIGH by clocking the $CLKADV$ signal. The output dynamic range of the DAC should be set as such that it covers the dynamic range of the $READLINE$ voltage as well as the mismatches.

The comparator outputs two signals, SGN and $LATCH$, where the SGN indicates whether the input is higher or lower than the previously converted value. The SGN output signal is determined during the first thermocode LSB and is locked for the rest of the AD-conversion. The $LATCH$ signal is set at this point only if the difference between the new input value and the previous ADC value is sufficiently small. The SGN and $LATCH$ signals are delivered to two separate counters, where the thermometer counter is advanced with every forthcoming $CLKADV$ clock edge until the $LATCH$ has been set. Similarly, the up/down counter is configured to count up or down based on the extracted SGN value and the counting is disabled when $LATCH$ signal is set to HIGH.

At the end of the ADC sequence, the event detection circuitry decides whether an event has occurred. This is

controlled by the EVT_THRS signal, which also sets the event detection magnitude. If an event has occurred, the event detection circuit ensures that the new ADC result is stored in the frame memory. Otherwise, the previous ADC result is retained. The frame memory consists of column memories pitch-matched to the column ADC. The frame memory access is synchronized with the image sensor row access so that matching values are always fed to the ADC, which is why asynchronous schemes [5], are impractical. Furthermore, $READLINE$ is multiplexed between two columns.

The raw logarithmic image stored in the frame memory is subject to significant fixed pattern noise (FPN). To tackle this issue, the raw image — which, in our case, is a flat image under constant illumination — is read off-chip, where the FPN correction image is calculated and sent back into the on-chip FPN compensation memory. The 6-bit FPN compensation values are then subtracted pixel-wise from the raw logarithmic grayscale values, creating an offset-compensated grayscale image.

Finally, the readout circuitry is shared between raw frame memory, offset compensation image, and event generation circuitry in a way that allows data from all three to be read off-chip.

IV. COMPARATOR

The comparator shown in Fig. 3, consists of a transconductance amplifier, a buffer, parallel PMOS and NMOS current sources, a dynamic latch for storing the sign information SGN , and digital logic for event magnitude measurement and generating the $LATCH$ signal. The positive input of the transconductance amplifier is connected to the $READLINE$ coming from the pixel array. The negative input is connected to the DAC such that the digital value from the previous corresponding AD-conversion is converted to analog voltage.

The initial step for AD-conversion is to convert the event sign information based on the voltage difference in amplifier inputs. In this step, none of the current sources drive the amplifier output. The sign bit SGN is stored inside the dynamic latch by pulsing WEO , and this information is used to control the selection of differential current source circuitry. For instance, a positive event would select the PMOS current source circuitry, thus closing the NMOS current sources, and vice versa. By opening the current sources individually, it is possible to detect the magnitude of the new event compared to the previously stored event. The control sequence of the current sources comes from a thermocode generator circuitry that uses four level thermometer coding thus having following digital output codes $\pm 0, \pm 1, \pm 2$ and ± 3 . Code ± 0 is treated as plain 0 although it also contains the sign information i.e. SGN bit value, without affecting the counter operation. Also, code ± 3 occurs when the comparator input voltage difference is large enough and effectively tells that the sensor voltage has changed more than comparison levels could detect. The transconductance amplifier converts the input voltage difference into output current and additional current, that is applied into the transconductance amplifier output node from

Fig. 2. Block level diagram of the column ADC, frame & compensation memories and readout.

Fig. 3. Simplified schematic of the comparator.

the current sources increases or decreases the voltage. The sign of the sum of currents is detected by the buffer and compared to the stored SGN bit. The final comparison value signal $LATCH$ controls the subsequent digital blocks in column ADC.

Additionally, it is possible to control the comparison levels using current sources. By increasing the reference current, the comparison level (i.e., LSB voltage) will also increase. Conversely, decreasing the reference current will decrease the LSB voltage. This is useful for selecting the proper biasing to suppress noise sensitivity within the comparator, as well as providing a means to track instantaneous sensor output faster. One way to select appropriate biasing and balancing the currents is to observe positive and negative events under constant illumination such that, for example, 10% of the image consists of positive events and another 10% consists of negative events.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS, MEASUREMENTS AND CHIP SUMMARY

The performance and characteristics of the proposed design were simulated with a mixed-mode simulator, where control signals were generated by a Verilog code block and the transistor-level design was simulated with an analog SPICE-simulator. Furthermore, the proper operation of the manufactured chip was demonstrated by reading out the raw image, events and FPN compensated image.

The comparator transfer curve characteristics were simulated with three different reference currents 100 nA, 200 nA, and 500 nA, demonstrating their effect on the comparison levels. The transconductance amplifier tail current was set to 15 μ A, thus reference currents have only a small impact on the total power consumption of the comparator. The comparator transfer curve simulation results are shown in Fig. 4 (a). The curves demonstrate that a higher reference current corresponds to a larger LSB step voltage.

The full sensor and column ADC transient simulation is presented in Fig. 4 (b). The sensor outputs a constant $READLINE$ voltage of 1.00 V until 20 μ s, after which it changes instantly to 1.02 V. At the beginning of the transient simulation, the frame memory as well as the up/down counter were initialized to a digital value which corresponds to a higher voltage than the sensor output in $READLINE$. It can be seen that the REF voltage, which is the output of the DAC, is initially at some high voltage level where it starts to approach the $READLINE$ voltage at constant voltage steps that correspond to -3 event magnitude. Approximately at 16.5 μ s, the REF voltage reaches the $READLINE$ voltage and the column ADC does not output events anymore. The next events that the system detects occur at 20 μ s when the $READLINE$ voltage changes instantaneously. In this case, it takes five ADC cycles to reach the readline voltage again and in every step, the event magnitude is detected as +3. In this simulation, the AD-

Fig. 4. Simulation and measurement results. (a) Simulated comparator transfer curves. (b) Transient simulation of column ADC tracking the *READLINE* voltage. (c) Raw logarithmic image. (d) Events generated by the event generation circuitry. (e) FPN corrected image.

Fig. 5. Partial chip image and floorplan.

conversion period was 280 ns. In practice, the time between consecutive AD-conversions is longer due to settling times of DAC output, *READLINE* voltage etc. In order to reach 5000 frames per second for 128 rows, the AD-conversion time for one row has to be lower than 1.5 μ s.

Fig. 4 (c), shows a raw logarithmic image read out from the pixel array and converted to digital with column-level ADC. It is evident that this image is deteriorated by significant FPN. Fig. 4 (d), shows events generated by the event generation circuitry. Note that the scene is in motion when the image is captured. Fig. 4 (e), shows FPN corrected image of the raw logarithmic image. This experiment showed that the pixel, ADCs, event generation and on-chip dynamic frame memory works. The FPN correction was carried off-chip. There is salt and pepper noise in the image. These noise occur in particular places, but they exhibit flickering so they are not present in every frame.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS.

Technology	180 nm CMOS
Supply voltage	1.8 V/3.3 V
Pixel area	10 μ m \times 10 μ m
Pixel power consumption ¹	70 nW
Col. ADC power consumption ¹	30 μ W
Dynamic range ¹	100 dB
Column ADC and memory area	20 μ m \times 1700 μ m
CMOS array resolution	128 \times 128
Achievable frame-rate ¹	up to 5000 FPS

¹ Simulated value at 5000 FPS.

The availability of compensated intensity image opens up the possibility to further analyse the spatial features of the image on-chip. The analysed results can be read out from the chip using faster readout method as compared to reading out the full intensity image and performing the analysis off-chip. In our measurements, the full intensity image is read out at 30 FPS.

The pixel array is 128 \times 128 pixels, and the designed chip image and floorplan are shown in Fig. 5. The performance characteristics are summarized in Table I.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented 128 \times 128 pixel CMOS event camera front-end, ADC based on column level multi-bit temporal difference event conversion and its FPN compensation that provides fast event detection as well as grayscale image information on a compact hardware. The proposed design was implemented in 180 nm CMOS technology. The operation was verified with a circuit simulator and measurements. Furthermore, the non-idealities such as mismatch variations and its compensation was analysed on hardware.

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